

Methods of developing oral and written speech of primary school students**MATYAQUBOVA FOTIMA URINBAYEVNA**

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Аннотация: В данной научной статье полностью разъяснено обучение учащихся начальных классов правилам написания сочинений, правилам красивого написания букв без орфографических ошибок.

Ключевые слова: Сосредоточение внимания на словарном значении слова эссе, звуке, фонетике, типах эссе, вежливости.

Abstract: In this scientific article, teaching elementary school students the rules of writing essays, the rules of writing letters beautifully without spelling mistakes is fully explained

Key words: Focusing on the dictionary meaning of the word essay, sound, phonetics, essay types, courtesy.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu ilmiy maqolada boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilariga insho yozish qoidalarini o'rgatish, harflarni imlo hatosiz chiroyli yozish qoidalari haqida to'liq yoritib berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Insho so'zining lug'aviy ma'nosi, tovush, fonetika, insho turlari, husnixatga e'tibor qaratish.

Orientalizing the meaning of the word "essay" when giving information about an essay works well. "Essay" is an Arabic word that means "to create", "to build", "to build", "to begin". An essay is a creative text - a small piece of work that demonstrates the student's skills and abilities to independently reveal a certain

topic, express his thoughts in written form correctly, fluently, and literately, and his knowledge on this topic. Just as a writer and a poet, a scientist and a reporter look at the work, scientific work, article they write with great responsibility, the student should prepare for it in every way before writing an essay. Because the essay is a reflection of the student's spirituality and wisdom. It reflects the student's knowledge, feelings, and skills to express their thoughts.

The essay is mainly of 3 types: Literary essay, Literary-creative essay, Free essay. Simple written images familiar to us from the first grade, stories based on pictures, and various letters. is also like an essay. But they cannot be called essays in the literal sense. Because in such written work, the student's independence and creativity are limited. 1. Essays on literary topics include topics explained by the teacher in class and noted in literature lessons. 2. When writing essays on a literary and creative topic, on the one hand, it is required to think about the information received as a separate topic in the lesson, and on the other hand, the student learned materials outside the class. When writing essays of the first type, the student's independent thinking is relatively limited. But this consideration should not lead to the conclusion that they do not require independent thinking. In the second type of essays, the student's independence is felt more vividly. Because the student's attitude to the topic is of primary importance when writing them. 3. Free essays are written on topics that are not directly mentioned in literature classes. Students are free to write on whatever topics they like. For example: dreams, choosing a profession, about the Motherland and other topics can be covered. Students should also learn the meaning of terms such as topic, plan, epigraph, thesis, evidence while developing the skills of writing an essay beginning with oral information or

a simple story, teaching the student to express his opinion as the grades go up, serving to form the personality of the student, expanding his worldview by advancing his mind, clarifying his thinking, and having an educational value. Essay is a very effective tool in forming a child's personality, it arouses emotions, mental independence, thinking, evaluation of what he has seen and learned, between events and events teaches to find cause-and-effect relationships, compare them, draw conclusions. The essay guides the student to organize his thoughts. Writing an essay and telling an oral story is the end of the work done earlier in the lesson. The generalizing role of the essay in the lesson increases depending on the level of mastery of skills in the field of connected speech. In the 2nd grade, usually one lesson is required to write an essay. 15-20 minutes from the second lesson, one or one-and-a-half lessons in grades 3-4, sometimes up to 2 lessons are allocated from the second lesson. Teaching students to write essays is one of the main tasks facing teachers of general education schools today. One of the important types of essays written in primary grades are essays based on the life experience of younger students.

The essay is the highest form of creative work and has a special place in school; all speech exercises are subordinated to the essay in a certain content. In the 1st grade, the essay begins with a small oral information and a passionate story, and turns into a serious planned intellectual work of educational and educational value, which serves to express one's opinion, to form the student's personality. Essay is a useful tool in the formation of personality, it arouses emotions, mental independence, thinking, evaluation of what has been seen and learned, observation, finding cause-and-effect connections between events, comparing them, teaches to

draw conclusions. Essay organizes thought, makes students believe in themselves, their power and potential. An essay is a creative work that requires the student to be active, interested, and think. Preparing material, organizing it, thinking about the composition and plan of the essay, defining logical connections, choosing words and phrases, making sentences and connecting them, checking spelling, etc. It requires from the student the ability to manage his spiritual activities along with the full use of his mental strength. In the essay, language theory is combined with speech experience. The reader loves the essay because it is independent, creative, and because he writes "his own". At all stages of school development, special importance is attached to the story-essay written independently by my child. In connection with the transition of schools to a new program designed for the development of students' speech, mental and creative growth, its importance has increased. The skills of subordinating the essay to a clear idea, collecting material, organizing and placing it, making a plan and writing based on the plan, using language tools in accordance with the content and speech situation, and improving the written essay are formed. In addition to these, "technical" tasks are also carried out, that is, when writing the text, attention to spelling rules and grammar, writing the text from paragraph to paragraph, observing the margin are also followed. It is classified according to the level, method of preparation, genre and language characteristics. The essay is divided into three according to the source of the material: 1) about what the student himself saw, heard, observed, excursions, games, Essay based on own experience and other living materials; 2) essay based on book material, pictures, film, play, teacher's story and other sources; 3) essay using material from various sources.

According to the level of independence, the method of preparation There are two types of essays: 1) an essay written for students of the class after collective preparation based on a common topic; 2) an individual essay written after individual preparation based on a specific topic. According to the genre, story, image, divided into discussion essays. In elementary grades, more use is made of the narrative essay, which contains elements of illustration and discussion. Classification of the essay helps to understand the educational tasks in depth and to choose methodical tools, as well as to distribute the types of work in the necessary direction. One of the important types of essays written in primary grades is an essay based on the personal life experience of a young student. Essays written based on pictures and observing nature are often held in schools, because pictures serve to enrich children's verbal creativity and imagination. Like watching pictures going on trips also has a positive effect on children's intuition. Aspects of life that have not yet been encountered in child education are revealed. The picture helps students to understand familiar events more deeply. Essay begins with small oral information or a simple story in the 1st grade, and as the grades go up, it teaches the student to express his opinion, serves to form the personality of the student, expands his worldview by advancing his mind, clarifies his thinking, and sharpens his vision. Essay is a very effective tool in the formation of a child's personality, it arouses emotions, encourages mental independence, thinking, evaluating what he has seen, experienced and mastered, events - teaches to find the cause-and-effect relationship between events, to compare them, to draw conclusions. The essay directs the student to organize his thoughts. Writing an essay and telling an oral story is the end of the work done earlier in the lesson. The generalizing role of the

essay in the lesson increases depending on the level of acquisition of skills in the field of connected speech. To write an essay in the 2nd grade, usually one lesson, but if necessary, 15-20 minutes from the second lesson, in 3-4 grades one or one and a half lessons, sometimes up to 2 lessons.

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